

SQUEEZE CAST MAGNESIUM COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Strengthening of light alloys with short fibres produces materials with an interesting range of properties. Such materials can be employed for highly stressed components in general engineering, aircraft and space, and automobile industry applications where weight saving is necessary.

Short fibre reinforced magnesium alloys possess much higher E-modulus, lower coefficient of thermal expansion and improved wear resistance in addition to an improvement in the mechanical properties at room and elevated temperature. Powder and liquid phase mixing of the fibres is possible as in infiltration of fibre preforms. The advantage of the preforms lie in its universal applicability as well as the possibility of graduated or partial component reinforcement. There are economic advantages due to simple procedures and low investment costs. In this work the structure, mechanical properties, wear resistance and thermal expansion of short fibre reinforced materials are presented and discussed. The influence of the matrix alloy on the properties is also presented. The preforms used were bonded Saffil fibre bondies with a fibre content of %.